

MAGNETO-CHEMICAL STUDIES IN VALENCY. PART V. VALENCY OF NICKEL, AND NATURE OF THE BOND IN ARSENICAL NICKEL ORES

BY PRIVADA RANJAN RĀY AND DWIJENDRA NATH SEN

Measurement of magnetic susceptibility of a specimen of arsenical nickel glance, NiAsS , and of a specimen of red nickel ore (kupfernickel), NiAs , gave moment values of $1.85\mu_B$ and $0.74\mu_B$ respectively. From this it has been concluded that in the former the nickel atom is in the trivalent state and it is covalently bound to arsenic atom in an octahedral configuration by means of d^2sp^3 hybrid bonds, while in the latter the bonds are metallic in character. The results are in good agreement with those deduced from a consideration of known interatomic distances and crystal structure determined by the X-ray method, as also with the general physical properties of the substances.

The valency state of the elements of the transitional series in their sulphide and arsenical ores, and the nature of linkage with which they bind the neighbouring sulphur and arsenic atoms, present a somewhat intriguing problem. Thus, for instance, iron pyrites, FeS_2 , which has been found by X-ray analysis to possess the characteristic pyrites structure with every iron atom bound octahedrally to six S-atoms (rather S_2) and each sulphur atom linked tetrahedrally to three iron atoms and one sulphur atom, is believed on the basis of their interatomic distances to consist essentially of covalent bonds with iron in the bivalent state. The fact that the substance is very feebly paramagnetic seems to support this idea, and Pauling ("The Nature of the Chemical Bond," 1940, p. 181) therefore assumes that the structure corresponds to the formation of $3d^24s4p^3$ bonds by Fe as in $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$. In hauerite, MnS_2 , which also crystallises in pyrites structure, it is argued from Mn—S interatomic distance, as determined by X-ray analysis, that the bonds are probably ionic, because the calculated octahedral covalent radius of bivalent manganese (1.26\AA approx.) is much lower than 1.55\AA deduced from the observed Mn—S distance of 2.59\AA . This is in good agreement with the result of magnetic measurement on the mineral, which gives a moment value of 6.1 Bohr for Mn (Elliot, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 59, 1958). It differs widely from the value of $1.73\mu_B$ expected for d^2sp^3 hybrid covalent bonds as in manganocyanide, $[\text{Mn}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$. On the other hand, it agrees closely with the moment value of 5.92 Bohr of manganous ion.

In arsenical nickel glance, NiAsS , which also forms pyrites type of crystal, it is believed from the known values of interatomic distance that the bonds are of covalent d^2sp^3 type as in FeS_2 with the nickel atom in the trivalent state. On this basis it should give a moment value of one promoted electron as shown below :

In kupfernickel or red nickel ore, NiAs , which crystallises in the nickel arsenide type, each As-atom is bound to six Ni-atoms at the corners of a trigonal prism and each nickel atom is octahedrally surrounded by six As-atoms. Here too, the nickel atom is

believed to be trivalent from the measured Ni—As distance. If it also forms covalent bond of d^2sp^3 type, it should likewise give a moment value of one unpaired electron (1.73 Bohr) as shown above. On the other hand, if the bonds in these two minerals be essentially ionic in character, then a trivalent nickel ion should give a moment value corresponding to three unpaired electrons, i.e., 3.88 Bohr according to Bose-Stoner's formula, as is evident from the following representation :

With a view to determining the valency state of nickel atom and the nature of the bond in these two arsenical nickel ores, it was considered desirable to measure the magnetic susceptibility of the substances. A sample of nickel glance supplied by the Geological Survey of India and a very pure sample of kupfernicker, obtained several years ago from a German firm, were analysed and their susceptibilities measured. The results are recorded below.

Arsenical Nickel Glance.

TABLE I

Constituent.	Per cent.	Atom or mol. ratio.
Ni	22.69	0.3868
As	45.10	0.60
S	19.40	0.606
Fe	5.80	0.1038
Co	2.98	0.05
SiO ₂	3.59	0.06
Total	99.56	

It appears from the atomic ratio of the constituents that the ore is not a pure nickel glance of formula, NiAsS, or even Ni(Fe,Co)AsS with nickel partially substituted by iron and cobalt by isomorphous replacement. It seems that the ore is admixed with minerals of the type Ni(Fe,Co)As₂ or/and Ni(Fe,Co)S₂.

Magnetic Measurement (Gouy's balance).—The finely powdered ore (1.04977 g.) experienced a pull of 40.4 mg. at 31.5°, the length of the column being 9.3cm. $H_{max} = 10.16 \times 10^3$ gauss.

$$\chi_g = \frac{18.6 \times 40.4}{1.04977 \times 1.019 \times (10.16 \times 10^3)^2} = 7.1214 \times 10^{-6}$$

Diamagnetic corrections = $\chi_m \times 10^6$

As = -43, Ni = -12, Fe = -12, Co = -12, S = -15, SiO₂ = -22.

Diamagnetic correction for χ_g calculated from the above values and the analytical composition of the ore amounts to 0.428×10^{-6} .

Hence, χ_g (corrected) = $(7.1214 + 0.428) \times 10^{-6} = 7.549 \times 10^{-6}$.

χ_a = susceptibility of the substance containing Ni_{0.716} + Co_{0.092} + Fe_{0.192} = 1g. atom of the metals = $7.549 \times \frac{100}{0.5406} \times 10^{-6} = 1396 \times 10^{-6}$

(0.5406 represents the sum of the number of atoms of Ni, Co and Fe present in 100g. of the ore).

$$\mu \text{ (effective)} = 2.84 \sqrt{1396 \times 304.5 \times 10^{-6}} = 1.85 \text{ approx.}$$

Kupfernickel

(Found: Ni, 43.95 As 56.00: NiAs requires Ni, 43.80, As 56.20 per cent).

Magnetic Measurement.—The ore (1.54068g) gave a pull of 11.04 mg. at 31° , the length of the column being 9.1 cm.

$$\chi_g = \frac{18.20 \times 11.04}{1.54068 \times 1.019 \times (10.16 \times 10^3)^2} = 1.24 \times 10^{-6}$$

$$\chi_m = 133.32 \times 1.24 \times 10^{-6} = 165.05 \times 10^{-6}$$

$$\text{Diamagnetic corrections} = -55 \times 10^{-6}$$

$$\chi \text{ (atom)} = (165.05 + 55) \times 10^{-6} = 220.05 \times 10^{-6}$$

$$\mu \text{ (effective)} = 2.84 \sqrt{220 \times 304 \times 10^{-6}} = 0.74$$

DISCUSSION

The nickel ore, kupfernickel, gives a very low moment value of 0.74 Bohr for nickel, which cannot be accounted for on the basis of ionic bond for the nickel atom either in the bi- ($\mu_B = 2.83$) or trivalent ($\mu_B = 3.88$) state. If the bonds be of the covalent d^2sp^3 type, the moment value for bivalent nickel would be 2.83 Bohr and for the trivalent complex it would be 1.73 Bohr. So the Ni—As bond in nickel arsenide or red nickel ore is neither ionic nor covalent, but presents a definite transition from the ionic type to the metallic character. This is further supported by the development of metallic or alloy-like properties in the compound, such as red metallic lustre, hardness or brittle character. Moreover, the fact that it can form solid solution with an excess of the transitional metals points in the same direction (Klemm and Shuth, *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1931, 203, 104). In consequence of the mutual interaction of the cation and the anion, the outermost electrons of the anion and cation lose their original hold on them and assume partially the character of metallic electrons. In fact, Goldschmidt (*Ber.*, 1927, 60, 1286) was the first to point out that due to such polarization phenomena metallic characters would be developed in substances of nickel arsenide structure, where a transitional metal of relatively small size was combined to a large readily polarizable element. The low co-ordination number of nickel in Ni—As, if we ignore the presence of two other nickel atoms as nearest neighbours, though reveals a departure from a purely metallic binding, nevertheless, that the structure is essentially metallic becomes evident from many of its properties, notably its magnetic moment. It may, therefore, be concluded that the Ni—As bond in kupfernickel is neither ionic nor covalent, but predominantly metallic representing a transition between the two, as a result of polarization. The question of valency of nickel atom does not, therefore, arise here.

The arsenical nickel glance, NiAsS, on the other hand, gives a fairly high magnetic moment value of 1.85 Bohr (approx.) showing that the bonds are not of the metallic type. The substance possesses a pyrites type of crystal structure, as stated before, and

it is known from the determination of interatomic distances by the X-ray method that the metal atom (Ni and therefore also Co and Fe which replace Ni isomorphously) occurs in the crystal in the trivalent state (cf. Pauling, "The Nature of the Chemical Bond", 1940, p. 183) and that as in pyrites each nickel atom is surrounded octahedrally by six AsS groups. If the bonds were ionic, the magnetic moment would have been much higher. For, trivalent nickel would give a moment value of 3.88 Bohr, corresponding to three unpaired electrons; trivalent cobalt would give a value of 4.90 Bohr, corresponding to four unpaired electrons; and trivalent iron would give a value of 5.92 Bohr, corresponding to five unpaired electrons on the basis of Bose-Stoner's formula. Hence, the moment value for the mineral under investigation would have been $0.715 \times 3.88 + 0.093 \times 4.90 + 0.192 \times 5.92 = 4.36$ Bohr approx. The determination of the radii of Ni atom in NiAsS by the X-ray method has shown that the metal is not only trivalent, but the structure of the crystal is essentially a homopolar one with some measure of metallic binding (cf. Pauling, *loc. cit.*). Hence, if the binding be covalent of the octahedral d^2sp^3 type, then the moment value for the substance under investigation should be 0.715×1.73 (corresponding to one unpaired electron in nickel) $+ 0.092 \times 0$ (diamagnetism for Co) $+ 0.192 \times 1.73$ (corresponding to one unpaired electron for Fe), i.e., equal to 1.57 Bohr approx. Trivalent nickel, cobalt and iron in octahedral complexes with d^2sp^3 bonds are known to show the moment values of 1.73, 0, and 1.73 respectively. Thus the calculated value of 1.57 Bohr for the mineral approaches the observed value of 1.85. The latter is, however, somewhat higher. This is presumably due to the presence of impurities like $Ni^{III}S_2$ and $Fe^{IV}As_2$, as already discussed in connection with the analytical results. The valences of the metal atoms in these substances, as indicated in their symbols, are those deduced from their interatomic distances by X-ray measurement (cf. Pauling, *loc. cit.*). The moment value of each of these substances is given by 2.83 Bohr, corresponding to the presence of two unpaired electrons, as the metal atoms in them are known to form octahedral complexes with d^2sp^3 bonds. Besides, it may also be pointed out here that CoS_2 , which might as well be present as an impurity in the nickel glance under examination, has been found to be ferromagnetic below 130° (Haraldson and Klemm, *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1935, 223, 409). The presence of a slight trace of CoS_2 as an impurity will, therefore, considerably enhance the moment value of the arsenical nickel glance.

It can thus be established from the magnetic measurement that in arsenical nickel glance, the metal-metalloid binding is essentially covalent of the octahedral d^2sp^3 type and the nickel atom is in the trivalent state as already suggested from a consideration of their interatomic distances by Pauling (*loc. cit.*).